
STRUCTURAL ADJUSTMENT PROGRAMME AND TIME SERIES PROPERTIES OF COCOA PRODUCTION, EXPORT AND PRICES IN WEST AFRICA (1961-2007): AN APPLICATION OF THE PERRON TEST

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the structure of the West African Cocoa Agriculture by analyzing fifteen pertinent annual series, namely; acreage, yield, producer price, quantity exported and export value of cocoa, in Ghana, Nigeria and Cote d'Ivoire during the 1961- 2007 period. The methodology used is that of Perron (1989) wherein he tests the null and alternative hypotheses of a unit root or `trend-stationary` series, respectively, in the presence of possible slope and/ level shifts. The results for the Perron unit root tests indicate that all the series are trend stationary rather than being differenced stationary with the exception of cocoa export in Cote d'Ivoire and Ghana, as well as cocoa export value in Nigeria. Meanwhile cocoa producer price in Nigeria, cocoa acreage, cocoa producer price and cocoa export in Ghana alongside cocoa export value in Cote d'Ivoire were still not stationary after the introduction of the broken trend and intercept variables into the Perron model. The Perron changing growth model also revealed that SAP, otherwise referred to as structural break significantly and positively affected cocoa yield in all of Ghana, Nigeria and Cote d'Ivoire. It also has a positive and significant effect on cocoa acreage in Nigeria. While Structural Adjustment programme also have a positive and significant effect on cocoa export in the three selected countries, it did not have a positive and significant effect on cocoa producer price in all the selected countries.

Key words: Structural break, Unit root, Cocoa, Market liberalization, Structural Adjustment Programme and ECOWAS

JEL Classification: C010, C220, Q110 and Q180

INTRODUCTION

There is very little debate regarding Africa's poor economic performance and the long-term nature of the decline in living standards, particularly during the 1980s. But controversy continues to surround the issue of which factors are responsible for the crisis. Oyejide(1990) identified two sharply contrasting views on the crisis and its causes which emerged in the 1980s. On the African side, the Organization of African Unit (OAU) articulated the Lagos Plan action (LPA) in 1980 which placed most of the plight of African economies on adverse external and climatic environment. Oyejide (1990) specifically identified the world recession, falling real commodity prices, declining export volume and terms of trade, rising interest rate and debt burden, as well draught as the major factor responsible for Africa's economic crisis. In comparison, the world bank Bergs report (World Bank, 1981) attributed most of the problems to domestic factors such as poor economic management, including overly expansionary fiscal and monetary policy, policies which reduced micro-economic efficiency through the introduction of various distortion both in the product and factor markets, policies producing export disincentives such as overvalued exchange rates and high-cost inefficient import-substitution industrialization, as well as inefficient public sector and parastatal activities.

According to Oyejide (1990), African governments acknowledge that poor domestic policies in the early 1980s have played a role in the economic crisis. In the same way, external commentators certainly acknowledge the impact of external and climatic constraints on the economies of SSA countries. In fact, some analysts have concluded that external shocks have been more important in determining the economic performance and external payment imbalances, although poor domestic policies have also impeded appropriate adjustment responses (Yagci, *et al* 1985). In any case, the

concession on both sides notwithstanding, the two contrasting views of the factors responsible for the crisis naturally led to marked differences in policy description. The African view enshrined in the Lagos Plan Action recommended the promotion of regional co-operation and integration based on an essentially inward looking strategy, which at the same time sought to put some distance between the alleged fragile, rigid and undiversified African economies and an “unreliable and hostile” external environment. The World Bank’s policy recommendation, on the other hand, has pointed in the opposite direction by urging the adoption of an outward-oriented strategy that would become operational through adjustment and appropriate domestic policy reforms.

However, policy reforms activities in the 1980-1989 periods show quite clearly that one of the contrasting views has won the day. Actual policy-reform efforts have focused primarily on the domestic front, thus giving the impression that SSA countries have either ignored or set aside the prescription of the Lagos Plan Action in favour of the World Bank’s recommendations. The reform involves a clear shift toward greater reliance on market forces and the price system, and toward an export-oriented strategy (Oyejide, 1990). What is less clear is the extent to which this radical shift in policy stance reflects a genuine conversion to an outward looking strategy or an involuntary acceptance of an externally imposed “conditionality”. Since virtually all of the on-going domestic policy-reform packages have been designed (partially or completely) and supported, in one way or another, by arrangement with World Bank and the International Monetary Fund, it may be presumed that external “advice”, if not pressure, has played an important role in bringing about many of the policy changes.

The economies of many of the SSA was majorly supported by exports of primary commodities such as cocoa and coffee play a key roles, often providing the major source of foreign exchange, government revenues, and employment. Commonly, the domestic markets for these commodities are subject to strict government controls (often implemented through government-owned marketing boards) over many of the production, marketing, and exporting activities.

Some SSA countries however, introduced measures to liberalize their commodity export markets under the structural adjustment programme (SAP) adopted by many of the SSA countries. The policy changes introduced included the removal of trade restrictions, price controls, and export taxes, and in some countries the state-owned marketing boards were abolished.

Meanwhile these policy changes, have led to concern about their impact on world prices of commodities such as cocoa and coffee and, in turn, on the countries exporting them. The policy changes have, in the main, encouraged production and exports of commodities and likely led to lower international commodity prices than would have otherwise occurred (Coleman *et al.*,1993)

From 1980s onwards, all countries in ECOWAS have been through a process of structural adjustment involving liberalization of the economy, devaluation of the currency and a range of associated measures to achieve the process of modernization like other Sub- Saharan African countries. Studies have shown that many ECOWAS countries have been remarkably successful, in generating rising level of output, in response to market demand at national, regional and global levels. However, there is need today to analyze the effects of these policies of stabilization and liberalization on agriculture in ECOWAS. More importantly, after over two decades of implementation of structural adjustment programs in ECOWAS, it is now appropriate to assess the effect these policy reforms have had on the agricultural export crops sector.

This study selects cocoa, which is an important export commodity in the West African sub-region which also holds considerable shares of the world market. Cocoa production in West Africa is concentrated in Cote d’Ivoire, Ghana and Nigeria. This study seeks to evaluate how the SAPs have affected the cocoa sub-sector in the sub-region. In order to meet this objective, this study empirically examined how SAP policies have affected cocoa acreage cultivated by farmers, cocoa yield, the domestic cocoa prices received by farmers, the quantity of cocoa exported and export value..

The plan of the paper is as follows. Section 2 describes materials and method involved which include the data source and their measurement with the procedure for testing the null hypothesis that the selected crop series have a unit root with a possible non-zero drift against the alternative that it is trend-stationary and experiences a one time change in the slope of its trend (with the implementation of SAP policy). Section 3 presents the Perron (1989) standard unit-root test results and

Perron (1989) unit root results with structural break coefficients. The findings are summarized and an interpretation of the results, as well as an assessment of the impact of the structural adjustment programme in the study countries is offered. The conclusion and policy recommendation to the work are offered in section 4

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data source and measurement.

This study is based on annual country level cocoa data pertaining to Cote d'Ivoire, Ghana and Nigeria for the period 1961- 2007 . The data were sourced from the FAOSTAT database of the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations. Data on exchange rate were taken from Penn World table of the Penn World database of the University of Pennsylvania. The own price data on price and quantities for Cocoa were used. The price and output indices were constructed using Laspeyres formular. The Laspeyres price and output indices were constructed as follows

$$P_t = \left[\frac{\sum P_1 Q_0}{\sum P_0 Q_0} \right] 100 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where

$\sum P_0$ = Total of previous year price

$\sum P_1$ = Total of current year price

$\sum Q_0$ = Total of previous year output

$\sum Q_1$ = Total of current year output

The period covers 1961 – 2007 with indices benchmarked to the year of adoption of the SAP Policy which is 1986 for Nigeria, 1983 for Ghana and 1994 for Cote d'Ivoire (i.e. $Q_0 = P_0 = Q_{1986} = P_{1986} = 100$ for Nigeria as an example).

Analytical Technique: The Perron’s test for Structural Break.

This study adopted the definition of Alemu, *et al* (2003) for “Structural Breaks”. The authors defined it, as “changes in economic systems”. The study, first focused on the measuring the significance of changes in economic systems (which was thereafter referred to as “breaks”) on trends in the agricultural GDP. Secondly, the study’s emphasis is on the sustained impact of those changes on economic systems in the agricultural GDP. The first was measured based on a regression analysis while the second was measured by conducting a time series analysis in order to determine to which class of non-stationary process that agricultural GDP belongs. Therefore, in this study, by “structural breaks”, policies changes of stabilization and market liberalization inherent of SAP in West Africa are referred to. This study examined how these policies changes affect the acreage, yield and producer price of cocoa in West Africa.

While Coleman *et al*, (1993) used the Counter – Factual Simulations technique to examine the effect of SAP on cocoa production and prices in West Africa with data covering only up to about 2002(which is just some few years after the adoption of SAP by many of the ECOWAS cocoa producing countries), this study employs, the Perron (1989) crash and changing growth model with data spanning up to 2007 which allows this study to examine the full effect of SAP.

In Perron (1989), the main concern is to determine whether structural breaks in a “trend stationary” series may reverse a failure to reject the null hypothesis of a unit root. That is, random walks with possible non-zero drift. Traditional tests for unit roots (such as Dickey-Fuller, Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Phillips-Perron) have low power in the presence of structural break. Perron (1989) showed that in the presence of a structural break in time series, many perceived nonstationary series were in fact stationary. Perron (1989) re-examined Nelson and Plosser (1982) data and found that 11 of the 14 important US macroeconomic variables were stationary when known exogenous structural break is included.

Perron (1989) allows for a one time structural change occurring at a time TB ($1 < TB < T$), where T is the number of observations.

According to Perron (1989), the null hypothesis considered is that a given series $\{y_t\}_0^T$ (of which a sample of size $T + 1$ is available) is a realization of a time series process characterized by the presence of a unit root and possibly a nonzero drift. However, the approach is generalized to allow a one-time change in the structure occurring at a time $T_B(1 < T_B < T)$. Three different models are considered under the null hypothesis: one that permits an exogenous change in the level of the series (a “crash”), one that permits an exogenous change in the rate of growth, and one that allows both changes. These hypotheses are parameterized as follows:

Null hypotheses:

$$\text{Model (A)} \quad y_t = \mu + dD(TB)_t + y_{t-1} + e_t, \quad \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

$$\text{Model (B)} \quad y_t = \mu + y_{t-1}(\mu_2 - \mu_1)DU_t + e_t, \quad \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

$$\text{Model (C)} \quad y_t = \mu + y_{t-1}dD(TB)_t + (\mu_2 - \mu_1)DU_t + e_t, \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

where

$$D(TB)_t = 1 \quad \text{if } t = T_B + 1, \quad 0 \text{ other wise;}$$

$$DU_t = 1 \quad \text{if } t > T_B, \quad 0 \text{ otherwise; and}$$

$$A(L)et = B(L)U_t,$$

$u_t \approx I.I.D.(0, \sigma^2)$, With $A(L)$ and $B(L)$ pth and qth order polynomials, respectively, in the lag operator L . The innovation series (e_t) was taken to be of the ARMA (p, q) type with the order p and q possibly unknown. This postulate allows the series (y_t) to represent quite general processes. More general conditions are possible and will be used in subsequent theoretical derivations.

Instead of considering the alternative hypothesis that y_t is a stationary series around a deterministic linear trend with time invariant parameters, he analyzed the following three possible alternative models:

Alternative hypotheses:

$$\text{Model (A)} \quad y_t = \mu_t + \beta t + (\mu_2 - \mu_1)DU_t + e_t, \quad \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

$$\text{Model (B)} \quad y_t = \mu + \beta_1 t + (\beta_2 - \beta_1)DT_t^* + e_t, \quad \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

$$\text{Model (C)} \quad y_t = \mu + \beta_1 t + (\mu_2 - \mu_1)DU_t + (\beta_2 - \beta_1)DT_t + e_t, \quad \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

Where

$$DT_t^* = t - T_B, \quad \text{and} \quad DT_t = t, \quad \text{if } t > T_B \text{ and } 0 \text{ otherwise.}$$

Here, T_B refers to the time of break i.e., the period at which the change in the parameters of the trend function occurs. Model (A) describes what we shall refer to as the crash model. The null hypothesis of a unit root is characterized by a dummy variable which takes the value one at the time of break. Under the alternative hypothesis of a “trend-stationary” system, Model (A) allows for a one-time change in the intercept of the trend function. For the empirical cases, T_B was the year 1929 and $\mu_2 > \mu_1$. Model (B) is referred to as the “changing growth” model. Under the alternative hypothesis, a change in the slope of the trend function without any sudden change in the level at the time of the break is allowed. Under the null hypothesis, the model specifies that the drift parameter μ change from μ_2 to μ_1 at time T_B . Model (C) allows for both effects to take place simultaneously, i.e. a sudden change in the level followed by a different growth path.

This study adopted Model C which allows for both effects to take place simultaneously, i.e. a sudden change in the level followed by a different growth path. Equation 8 below is the Perron’s equation for unit-root test.

$$y = \mu + \beta t + \alpha y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k c \Delta y_{t-i} + \ell_t \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

However, when a policy shift variable and a variable to examine possible change in intercept are included, the equation becomes,

$$y = \mu + \beta t + \theta DU_{1t} + \gamma DT1 + \alpha y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k c \Delta y_{t-i} + \ell_t \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

Where γ = coefficient for growth change variable DT, the dummy for structural break (SAP in this case). Model (C) above allows for both effects to take place simultaneously, i.e. a sudden change in the level followed by a different growth path. Where, TB is the date of implementation of SAP policy in the selected ECOWAS countries. The summation sign contains the relevant number of lagged difference terms (which will be determined for each of the series to be considered by using the Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC)).

The estimation and interpretation of this equation for each of the series will be a means of evaluating the effect of SAP Policy on the cocoa series of selected ECOWAS countries. The significance of α and γ terms are of particular importance. A significant γ coefficient indicate the presence of a structural break (which implies that SAP policy significantly affect the variable in question). A α significantly close to one indicates the presence of a unit root. That is the series is the series is differenced- stationary rather than trend stationary. The hypothesis is that many series may have α close to one in a normal ADF test with an intercept and time trend, but that when a shift parameter is included and is significant, the α term may no longer be significantly close to one.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Perron structural break test Results for Nigeria

Tables 1 and 2 show the Perron’s structural break test for cocoa series in Nigeria. Table 1 is the Perron’s unit root test for cocoa series while table 2 is the model estimates for the Perron unit root test but with broken trend and intercept included. From table 1, cocoa yield (LY_{co}), could not reject the null hypothesis of unit root. While cocoa producer price in Nigeria has significant α value that is close to 1, the coefficient of α for cocoa yield (LY_{co}) has coefficient that is significantly different from 1. After the introduction of SAP (which is the growth change variable with time of break at 1986) and trend shift variables, some remarkable differences were observed in the table and are as explained below.

1. Cocoa Acreage

Cocoa acreage has no definite solution for the Perron unit root test. The solutions obtained were outrageous. This result goes along with the ADF unit root test as cocoa acreage in the ADF unit root test is not stationary at levels and even after first differencing. Hence cocoa acreage was dropped from the analysis.

2. Cocoa Yield

The α coefficient for cocoa yield (LY_{co}) in the Perron unit root test for cocoa series in Nigeria is 0.700. However, after the introduction of the broken trend and intercept variables in the Perron unit root equation, a positive and significant coefficient was observed for the SAP variable (γ). The coefficient of 0.032 which is significant at 1% shows that there is an increase in the yield on cocoa in Nigeria after the introduction of SAP in that country. The result suggests that market liberalization which is one of the major features of SAP encouraged increased cocoa production through intensification of inputs and not necessarily as a result of increased acreage cultivated.

3. Cocoa Producer price

The cocoa producer price has a unit root as shown in Table 1. However after the introduction of the broken trend and intercept shift variables, the coefficient of α significantly dropped from 0.794 to 0.600. Hence cocoa producer price as

the Perron unit root test shows is differenced stationary. The coefficient for the SAP (trend shift variable γ) is 0.015 and it is not significant. At the introduction of SAP in Nigeria, production increased and producer price increased also. However, with time the quality of cocoa bean exported from Nigeria began to fall due to the abolition of the marketing boards that has hitherto been responsible for quality control. Consequently, the producer price of Cocoa in Nigeria has fallen over the years and farmers are now at the mercy of the discouraging international price. This study supports the theory that liberalisation has led to declining quality which reduces the premiums available on international markets for cocoa. Cocoa marketing boards were used to prevent the sale of small beans and ensured tight quality control; the restrictions were however lifted with liberalisation and market deregulation. No alternative systems have been put into place in Nigeria and other cocoa-producing West African countries (with the exception of Ghana, which still keeps government imposed quality controls)..

4. Cocoa Export

The α coefficient for cocoa beans exported ($Lqex$) in the Perron unit root test for cocoa series in Nigeria is 0.980. However, after the introduction of the broken trend and intercept variables in the Perron unit root equation, the coefficient of α became 0.299 which shows that $Lqex$ is differenced stationary rather than being trend stationary. A positive and significant coefficient was also observed for the SAP variable (γ). The coefficient of 0.052 which is significant at 5% shows that there is a significant increase in the quantity of cocoa exported in Nigeria after the introduction of SAP. Market liberalization significantly increased quantity cocoa beans available for export. This finding is in agreement with the effect of SAP on cocoa yield in 1 above.

5. Value of Cocoa Exported

The α coefficient for cocoa beans exported ($Lvex$) in the Perron unit root test for cocoa series in Nigeria is 0.715. After the introduction of the broken trend and intercept variables in the Perron unit root equation, the coefficient of α became 0.452 which shows that $Lvex$ is differenced stationary. However, a negative but insignificant coefficient was observed for the SAP variable (γ). This suggests that there is a decrease in the value of cocoa exported in Nigeria after the introduction of SAP. This as explained in (b) is as a result a fall in the producer price of cocoa received by farmers which results from fall in the quality of exported cocoa beans after the liberalization of the exports crops market in Nigeria.

3.2 Perron structural break test Results for Ghana

From table 1, all the series with the exception of cocoa yield (LY_{co}) could not reject the null hypothesis of unit root. While all other variables have significant α values that are close to 1, the coefficient of α for cocoa yield (LY_{co}) is 0.355 and it is not significant at 5%. This shows that cocoa yield is trend stationary rather than differenced stationary. However, after the introduction of SAP (which is the growth change variable with time of break at 1983) and trend shift variables, some remarkable differences were observed in the table and are as explained below.

1. Cocoa Acreage

After the introduction of the SAP and intercept shift variable, there was a significant drop in the value of α from 0.879 to 0.602. This shows that cocoa acreage (LA_{co}) in Ghana is differenced stationary. There was also a significant growth in the acreage of cocoa cultivated as shown in the coefficient for the trend variable. The coefficient is 0.026 and it is significant at 5%. This result further confirmed the fact that SAP (γ) has significantly increased cocoa production in Ghana. Among all cocoa producing West African countries, Ghana is still the only country where cocoa producers are still enjoying favourable producer prices due to the structure and mode of implementation of SAP in Ghana.

2. Cocoa Yield

The α coefficient for cocoa yield (LY) in the Perron unit root test is 0.355. However, after the introduction of the broken trend and intercept variables in the Perron unit root equation, a significant coefficient was observed for the SAP variable (γ). The coefficient of 0.020 which is significant at 1% shows that there is a significant increase in the yield on

cocoa in Ghana after the introduction of SAP in that country. Since a significant increase in the acreage of cocoa cultivated in Ghana has been observed after the introduction of the SAP variable (γ), it then follows that market liberalization which is one of the major features of SAP encouraged increased cocoa production through intensification of inputs and not necessarily as a result of increased acreage cultivated.

3. Cocoa Producer price

Cocoa producer price has a unit root as table 1 below shows. However after the introduction of the broken trend and intercept shift variables, the coefficient of α significantly dropped from 0.828 to 0.683. Hence cocoa producer price as the Perron unit root test shows is differenced stationary. The coefficient for the SAP (trend shift variable γ) is -0.021 although it is not significant. One could understand why the coefficient for the effect of SAP on cocoa producer price in Ghana is negative (although not significant) if we consider the fact that the introduction of SAP generally brought about fall in the producer price of many export crops (resulting from the fall of the grade of exported crops) among the adopting countries due to the removal of control standards which was the duty of the erstwhile commodity boards which. However in Ghana, although the SAP policy was also adopted, the commodity boards were left in place, although significant amount of cocoa revenue is still lost to cocoa bean smuggling into Cote d'Ivoire. This understandably will be affecting the income of other cocoa farmers.

4. Cocoa Export

The α coefficient for cocoa beans exported ($Lqex$) in the Perron unit root test for cocoa series in Ghana is 0.905. However, after the introduction of the broken trend and intercept variables in the Perron unit root equation, the coefficient of α became 0.193 which shows that $Lqex$ is differenced stationary. A positive and significant coefficient was also observed for the SAP variable (γ). The coefficient of 0.076 which is significant at 1% shows that cocoa export significantly increased in Ghana after the introduction of SAP. Market liberalization significantly increased quantity cocoa beans available for export.

5. Value of Cocoa Exported

The α coefficient for value of cocoa beans exported ($Lvex$) in the Perron unit root test for cocoa series in Ghana is 0.905. After the introduction of the broken trend and intercept variables in the Perron unit root equation, the coefficient of α became 0.785 which is still not significantly different from 1. This shows that $Lvex$ is stationary at levels. However, a positive but insignificant coefficient was observed for the SAP variable (γ). This suggests that although SAP significantly increased the quantity of cocoa exported in Ghana, it did not increase the export value. This will be understood if we consider the fact that the Ghanaian COCOBOD is subsidizing price of cocoa received by farmers for up to 50%.

3.3 Perron structural break test Results for Cote d'Ivoire

From table 1, all the series, i.e cocoa yield (LY), cocoa acreage (LA) and cocoa producer price (LP) rejected the null hypothesis of unit root. By implication, the coefficient of α for the variables listed above have coefficients that are significantly different from 1. This shows that these variables as the Perron unit root test has shown are trend stationary rather than differenced stationary. However, after the introduction of SAP (which is the growth change variable with time of break at 1994) and trend shift variables, some remarkable differences were observed in the table and are as explained below.

1. Cocoa Acreage

After the introduction of the SAP and intercept shift variable, there was a significant drop in the value of α from 0.419 to 0.136. This shows that cocoa acreage (LA) in Cote d'Ivoire is stationary around a linear deterministic trend. There was also a positive growth in the acreage of cocoa cultivated as shown in the coefficient for the trend variable. The coefficient is 0.024 although it is insignificant. This result further confirmed the fact that SAP (γ) have a positive effect on cocoa production in Cote d'Ivoire.

2. Cocoa Yield

The α coefficient for cocoa yield (LY) in the Perron unit root test for cocoa series in Cote d'Ivoire is -0.120. However, after the introduction of the broken trend and intercept variables in the Perron unit root equation, a positive and significant coefficient was observed for the SAP variable (γ). The coefficient of 0.011 which is significant at 5% shows that there was a significant increase in the yield on cocoa in Cote d'Ivoire after the introduction of SAP in that country. Market liberalization which is one of the major features of SAP encouraged increased cocoa production through intensification of inputs.

3. Cocoa Producer price

Cocoa producer price in Cote d'Ivoire does not have unit root. By implication, it is stationary around a linear deterministic trend. However after the introduction of the broken trend and intercept shift variables. The coefficient for the SAP (trend shift variable γ ,) is -0.024 and it is significant at 5%.

4. Cocoa Export

In Cote d'Ivoire, the α coefficient for cocoa beans exported ($Lqex$) in the Perron unit root test is 0.799 and it is significantly different from zero. However, after the introduction of the broken trend and intercept variables in the Perron unit root equation, the coefficient of α became 0.289 which shows that $Lqex$ is differenced stationary rather than being trend stationary. A positive and significant coefficient was also observed for the SAP variable (γ). The coefficient of 0.058 which is significant at 1% shows that there is a significant increase in the quantity of cocoa exported in Cote d'Ivoire.

5. Value of Cocoa Exported

The α coefficient for cocoa beans exported ($Lvex$) in the Perron unit root test for cocoa series in Cote d'Ivoire is 0.836. However, when the broken trend and intercept variables were introduced in to the Perron unit root equation, the coefficient of α became 0.799 and it is still significantly close to one. However, a negative but insignificant coefficient was observed for the SAP variable (γ). This suggests that there is a decrease in the value of cocoa exported in Cote d'Ivoire after the introduction of SAP.

CONCLUSION.

The internal and external imbalances created as a result of price distortions of the 1980s prompted the introduction of a structural adjustment programme by the ECOWAS countries with one of its major policy objectives being the market liberalization of agricultural exports and food crops. The paper examined the present situation in the West African cocoa agriculture and concludes that despite about two decades of operating SAP and economic liberalization in ECOWAS, the SAP policy is not achieving its intended purpose. Results suggests that exchange rate and price reforms under structural adjustment are, in many cases, not having their intended effects in stimulating favourable prices to the producers. However, where macroeconomic reforms, which include currency devaluation, stimulated export-because of which case one cannot say that exchange rate reforms are totally contractionary- the price received by the producers did not justify market liberalization and exchange rate reforms in the long- run. One qualification to this conclusion is that farmers are indeed responsive, but the exchange rate devaluation and market liberalization of SAP not sufficient to bring about the desired positive price responsiveness of the West African cocoa sub - sector.

Policy recommendation

Complementary interventions, to improve structural factors such as infrastructure, marketing, access to inputs and credit, improved production technology etc, can be expected to make producers much more responsive.

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Table 1 : Perron's structural break test for Cocoa in Selected West African Countries.
(Broken intercept and trend not included)

$$Y_t = \mu + \beta t + \alpha Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k C \Delta Y_{t-1}$$

Variables	μ	β	α	K
Nigeria				
<i>LY</i>	5.486 (6.726)	0.004 (1.434)	0.700 (2.973)	0
<i>Lρ_{eo}</i>	1.045 (2.507)	-0.007 (-1.988)*	0.794 (9.615)***	1
<i>Lvex</i>	5.410 (2.768)**	0.003 (0.806)	0.715 (6.868)***	0
<i>Lqex</i>	0.119 (0.041)	0.005 (1.272)	0.980 (4.143)	5
Ghana				
<i>LA</i>	1.677 (1.679)	0.0006 (-0.039)	0.879 (12.488)***	0
<i>LY</i>	5.034 (7.050)	0.005 (2.378)**	0.355 (3.804)	0
<i>Lρ_{eo}</i>	0.889 (2.152)	-0.007 (-1.849)*	0.828 (10.260)***	1
<i>Lvex</i>	2.505 (1.907)*	0.0056 (1.593)	0.796 (7.400)***	1
<i>Lqex</i>	1.105 (0.927)	0.004 (1.611)	0.905 (9.627)***	2
Cote d'Ivoire				
<i>LA</i>	5.968 (4.369)	-0.0001 (-0.043)	0.419 (3.129)	0
<i>LY</i>	9.194 (7.605)	0.015 (6.951)**	-0.120 (-0.807)	1

Source: Data analysis, 2009

NB :t-values in parenthesis critical

t – Values for α taken from Perron's (1989) table. Critical t-values: 1% = 4.24 5% = 3.95 $\lambda = 0.48$

Table 2: Perron's structural break test for Cocoa in Selected West African Countries. (Broken intercept and trend included)

$$Y_t = \mu + \beta t + QDU \ 1 + \delta DT \ 1 + \alpha Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k c \Delta Y_{t-1}$$

Variables	μ	β	θ	δ	α	k	λ
Nigeria							
<i>LY</i>	6.566 (9.326)	-0.020 (-3.626)***	0.214 (2.328)**	0.032 (4.012)***	0.208 (2.361)	0	
<i>Lρ_{eo}</i>	1.751 (3.328)	0.01 (1.167)	-0.324 (-2.053)**	-0.015 (-1.521)	0.600 (4.855)**	1	
<i>Lvex</i>	8.474 (3.332)	0.002 (1.752)	-0.483 (-1.918)	-0.005 (-0.330)	0.452 (3.891)	0	
<i>Lqex</i>	8.923 (1.842)	-0.030 (-2.652)	0.011 (0.071)	0.052 (2.842)**	0.299 (0.744)	5	
Ghana							
<i>LA</i>	5.753 (2.944)	-0.012 (-2.022)**	-0.171 (-1.436)	0.026 (2.542)**	0.602 (4.448)***	0	
<i>LY</i>	5.192 (7.946)	-0.011 (-2.118)**	0.143 (1.666)	0.020 (3.081)***	0.358 (4.204)	0	
<i>Lρ_{eo}</i>	1.391 (2.550)	0.010 (0.841)	-0.240 (-1.407)	-0.021 (-1.205)	0.683 (5.201)***	1	
<i>Lvex</i>	2.651 (1.489)	0.006 (0.407)	-0.058 (-0.316)	0.004 (0.300)	0.785 (5.150)***	1	
<i>Lqex</i>	10.634 (3.937)***	0.036 (3.569)	-0.146 (-1.167)	0.076 (3.978)***	0.193 (0.942)	2	
Cote d'Ivoire							
<i>LA</i>	8.694 (5.792)	0.04 (2.339)**	-0.663 (-3.190)***	0.024 (1.315)	0.136 (0.900)	0	
<i>LY</i>	10.232 (8.818)	-0.014 (-1.700)*	0.013 (0.293)	0.011 (2.382)**	-0.240 (-1.700)	1	
<i>Lρ_{eo}</i>	2.183 (3.692)	0.003 (0.452)	0.251 (1.081)	-0.024 (0.997)	0.504 (3.813)	0	
<i>Lvex</i>	2.488 (1.956)	0.020 (1.299)	-0.053 (-0.279)	0.010 (0.493)	0.799 (6.333)***	1	
<i>Lqex</i>	7.960 (3.88)***	0.050 (3.828)***	0.194 (1.608)	0.058 (3.718)***	0.289 (1.569)	3	

Source: Data analysis, 2009

t-values in parenthesis. Critical t – values for α taken Perron (1989) table, Critical t-values: 5% = 4.24 1% = 4.90 λ = 0.48

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